

Electionem per revelationem: Truth, charisma, and the exhaustion of discernment in post-totalitarian modernity

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Abstract

Recent presidential elections in Romania reveal not only institutional and political tensions, but a deeper anthropological and epistemological crisis: the erosion of discernment as a condition of freedom. Electoral choice, traditionally understood as a rational act of deliberation, increasingly functions as a form of affective recognition, borrowing symbolic legitimacy from religious language rather than from argument and knowledge. We propose a social-theological and epistemological analysis of this phenomenon, structured around five interconnected dimensions: the post-totalitarian fragility of freedom and the delegation of judgment; the absolutization of political charisma and the logic of false recognition; the role of digital technologies in accelerating post-rationality and cognitive fatigue; the illicit symbolic transfer between religion and politics; and, finally, an anthropological diagnosis of the post-totalitarian mind, marked by the loss of epistemic humility. Our central argument is that contemporary political dysfunction cannot be explained solely by manipulation or institutional failure, but by the weakening of the subject's capacity to know. Where truth is reduced to affective intensity or sacralized authority, freedom survives only as procedure, not as lived responsibility.

Keywords

Social theology; post-totalitarianism; discernment; charisma; digital culture

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Introduction: Truth, freedom, and the fatigue of discernment

More than three and a half decades after the symbolic collapse of the communist regime, Romania continues to speak extensively about freedom while understanding very little of it. Yes, we have institutions, procedures, periodic elections—in short, we have the complete décor of a functional democracy. What is missing, however, is the difficult and rare element: a mind capable of bearing freedom. Freedom is neither an emotional state, nor a collective outburst, nor an ornamental value. It is a permanent tension, not artificial, but deeply anchored in anthropological data. Although apparently simple, the human desire for freedom is neither shallow nor irrelevant. Yet the tensions that accompany freedom are exhausting, frequently producing insomnia and, in any case, diminishing democratic appetite. Human beings desire freedom and protection. How, then, can these be reconciled? Anticipating part of an answer, one might point to the danger of personal disengagement from freedom, from which we take—much like from democracy—only the advantages, relying on the assumption that both freedom as a virtue and democracy as its public organization are grounded primarily in institutions. Yet this is precisely what fails to occur, especially in countries with a long struggle for freedom but with democratic institutions still undergoing consolidation.

At a theoretical and analytical level, this is precisely what transitology—a field of political studies that crystallized in the 1970s–1990s—has consistently shown (O’Donnell, Schmitter 1986; Linz, Stepan, 1996; Merkel, 1999; Krastev, 2017; Bendel et al., 2002; Pllack et al, 2001, Leb, Preda, 2003; Mungiu, 2013). One of its only apparently banal conclusions demonstrates that the transition from authoritarianism to democracy, whether in Eastern Europe or Latin America, but also in South Africa or other parts of the world, represents an extremely fragile structural process, marked by discontinuities, regressions, and normative ambiguities. O’Donnell spoke explicitly of “delegative democracies”, in which elections coexist with persistent authoritarian reflexes, while Schmitter emphasized the contingent nature of transitions, dependent on negotiations, pacts, and compromises that in no way guarantee the internalization of democratic values. In this key, the collapse of a regime does not entail the disappearance of its political anthropology: obedience, dependence on protection, avoidance of individual responsibility, belief in state paternalism grafted onto nationalism—as was the case in Romania—often survive long after constitutional change.

This resilience is all the more dangerous insofar as certain reflexes appear to have disappeared or faded over time—such as the rejection of Russian tutelage in favor of pro-Europeanism—only to return later with reversed polarities, as in the current sovereigntist discourse, under the guise of an alleged “awakening of conscience” meant to re-teach us a so-called “Russian wisdom.” In other words, transition becomes, as Linz observed, not merely a matter of institutional engineering, but a test of collective moral maturation, in which freedom is experienced more as risk than as resource. Where this test is not fully traversed, democracy remains procedural, and freedom is tolerated only insofar as it can be delegated, cushioned, or replaced by new forms of symbolic tutelage.

Returning to fatigue as a chronic condition of contemporary Romania, it is rarely acknowledged as such. Instead, it is masked, denied, yet lived through moralizing discourses, repeated invocations of civic education—difficult to articulate in a non-partisan manner—or through the identification of convenient culprits, successively and repeatedly externalized: elites, the media, foreign influences, and, at the limit, “the Russians”. Never the real, penal culprits, from former secret police to corrupt actors—a tautology, of course. All these may be real factors, yet they never constitute the core of the problem. Here two lines intersect: on the one hand, recovery from the communist experience; on the other, the fatigue of modernity as a broader system. This brings us to the far more uncomfortable core from which the decryption of everyday political movements must begin.

Put succinctly: freedom has rarely been rigorously linked to truth. It has instead been understood as the product of the emancipation of reason, human autonomy, and the inalienable right to live without socially imposed constraints—often without clear ethical articulation, as Habermas would put it. Consequently, freedom has been claimed, celebrated, suffered for, violently paid for with lives, symbolically consumed, proclaimed, adored—but rarely assumed and cultivated as a demanding cognitive exercise, corrective and constant, practically without alternatives. The consequences of this divorce between freedom and reason, between the personal and the impersonal, are visible: truth has become information, and freedom a context; reason itself has led to irrational excesses, like all excesses, atheism no more having produced greater humanism or more democracy. On the contrary, as Casanova also confirms (Casanova, 2009).

However reluctant we may be to religiously contextualize a theme that appears to belong exclusively to political studies, recourse to revealed texts proves—also in the case of these pages of minimal theoretical framing—not only unavoidable, but above all useful and suggestive. Religion has been, is, and will continue to be invoked in every possible sense, as Casanova and others have shown: as witness, or simply as instrument, not infrequently with its tacit consent or through the absence of an intelligent response commensurate with the ideological age. Thus, the Gospel formulates unequivocally and without detour the essential condition of the freedom proclaimed by Christ: “You will know the truth, and the truth will make you free” (John 8:32). The order is as evident as it is decisive and cannot be inverted without consequences. It is not freedom that produces truth, but truth—known, that is, discerned, tested, appropriated, lived, even witnessed martyrially—that makes freedom possible, paradoxically even beyond the body and the material benefits of a free life. The inversion of this order transforms freedom into an impulse, an affective reaction, or a collective resentment that will, sooner or later, be delegated to someone else—given away quite literally for free, despite an initial resistance that will eventually be stifled. Yes, as we know, this unequal ontological exchange—freedom in return for security—is usually made generously and with foolish enthusiasm. Yet whoever claims to be right uncritically, that is, in the absence of freedom, regardless of regime or context, will be in error and will kill—if they have not already done so (Berdyayev, 2010).

For his part, the Apostle Paul formulates, in a sober epistemic key, an ethics of cognitive responsibility: “Test everything; hold fast to what is good” (1 Thess 5:21). Not “feel,” not “resonate,” not “recognize,” not “be moved,” not project your dreams, nor replace salvation at the end of the road with contingent saviors. No. Test, pause, judge, look at what lies behind words and behind those who utter them, sometimes with great oratorical talent—that is, discern. Accept loss, if necessary now or inevitably later, and retain the power to question yourselves, to be critical first of all toward yourselves—the best school for being critical of others. Yet precisely this continuous, exhausting exercise—without being a psychosis or a deconstructionist fashion—has today become undesirable, because it demands time, formation as such, regardless of one’s register of knowledge or position within the community; in other words, patience and the acceptance of the seemingly banal fact of being wrong. We should therefore not be surprised that, in a culture of immediate reaction, of acceptance or rejection within a second, of instant approval or dismissal, discernment and analysis of any kind appear as obstacles rather than virtues—literally getting in the way by slowing down and complicating life.

Nor was this problem thematized only by Christianity. The Old Testament world had already articulated it with striking concision. The Book of Proverbs offers a lucid diagnosis of this condition: “The simple believes everything” (Prov 14:15). Not out of malice or stupidity, but because judgment is unexercised, largely due to the social stratification of access to knowledge, resulting in needs and

biological urgencies replacing judgments and criteria, interests replacing values, impulses replacing filtered sentiments, situational intelligence replacing destinal wisdom. To believe without testing—a formula wrongly turned into a pseudo-biblical quotation—is more comfortable than bearing the risk of truth, with or without a capital letter. Where this reflex becomes dominant and gregarious, freedom ceases to be a practice. It becomes what is worst for the bond between words and life: a slogan, the hardening or petrification of the mind that Christ reproached in the religious nomenclature of the Old Testament. Taken together, the propagandistic discourse about freedom and the formalism that replaces authentic religious life end up celebrating, crudely and absurdly, the manifest absence of freedom itself—of life. It is void and death (von Rad, 1970; Brueggemann, 1997; Dell, 2006).

By way of a provisional conclusion: if truth is the condition of freedom, and freedom presupposes judgment, then the fundamental question is not why political deviations occur, but why judgment grows weary, why it flickers, why it gasps for breath. The answer cannot be found exclusively in recent events, but in a longer history of the delegation of discernment—one that begins before technology, before charisma, and even before modernity, but which, in the post-totalitarian and post-modern context (so many failures combined!), acquires a specific and dangerous form. An existential one.

Post-totalitarian freedom: The fear of judgment and the delegation of discernment

There is, as has been observed, a psychological and political trait common to societies emerging from a totalitarian regime: freedom is desired, even longed for, yet judgment is avoided, dulled, or put to sleep—hence the flight from memory, from responsibility, and from (possible) guilt. After decades of imposed truth, as under communism, freedom appears not as an exercise of responsibility but merely as the suspension of constraint. From here arises the confusion between liberation and freedom, which soon—though not immediately—comes to be perceived negatively, as pressure: the pressure to assume decisions, consequences, and one’s own contribution, not only at the ballot box, but daily, within the family, at the workplace, in society at large, and even within the community of faith.

This discreet shift from the desire for freedom to the rejection of its direct, personal exercise explains why, once achieved—most often at the cost of victims—freedom begins to grow weary, first procedurally and soon existentially, eventually being, as has been said, almost given away “symbolically,” for free, to those who know what to do with it. There is hardly a more vitiated principle than that of blind, automatic delegation of power, whereby delegates take not only votes, but also the minds of those who delegate. Under such conditions, it is futile to accuse only those “at the top,” as long as guilt “at the bottom” is ignored or relativized through the familiar formula that there was supposedly no alternative, that between two evils the lesser one was chosen, and so on. In other words, those who live freedom deficiently “from below,” abusively self-reduced, generate as their symmetry an authority that is itself abusive—and, at times, legitimately so. There could hardly be a more convincing demonstration of the fact that the sleep of reason—especially in the post-traumatic case of memory refused through the dilation of the present (“why care about yesterday when today presses upon us?”)—gives birth to monsters even under conditions of formal freedom (Assmann 2006, 2013; Judt, 2005; Preda, 2021).

The biblical text that captures this situation with unsettling clarity reads: “Appoint for us a king to judge us” (1 Samuel 8:5). This is the request of the Jewish people at the zenith of Solomonic peace, at a time of the perpetually postponed construction of the Temple in Jerusalem, in a period of peace and—without distorting the historical reality—of freedom. Under such reassuring circumstances, they desired a “central” leader, a father figure who, like any summit, might function in times of storm as a

lightning rod: a guardian of faith, implicitly a “mediator” toward God, and also a guarantor of memory. As we know from the broader biblical context, this request also expressed the desire to fulfill the covenant with God, by instituting a dynastic power once the place of worship was established, thus exiting the long series of inter-tribal conflicts that had weakened—and would continue to weaken—the chosen people, delivering them to all kinds of oppressions, from repeated exile to the Roman occupation in the time of Christ. God’s response to the request for a king is neither delayed nor authoritarian in the form of a prohibition. Rather, it is a calm description of consequences: God does not refuse, but specifies—“this is what your king will do”—he will take, tax, mobilize, and subject. The conclusion is unmistakable: “and you shall be his slaves” (1 Samuel 8:17). The text does not describe an abuse, but the internal logic of delegating discernment. When judgment is handed over, freedom does not disappear abruptly; it gradually transforms into dependence. This is not evil in itself—it may be called the culture of normality, even the banality of the good, to paraphrase Arendt’s formulation regarding evil—but it inherently contains the betrayal of freedom by those who, through delegation, through king or leader, feel “relieved” of the complications that freedom entails (Brueggemann, 1990; McCarter, 1980; Halbertal, 1997; Ravasi, 2010).

This logic of entrusting power and leadership is fundamentally different from totalitarian coercion. Whereas totalitarianism imposes truth—or rather, the lie masquerading as truth—post-totalitarianism avoids it. In the first case, judgment is annulled through fear; in the second, it is abandoned through comfort. The result, however, converges: the human subject emerges weakened, reduced to a formal, statistical actor. In the Romanian context, this mutation is visible in the way political freedom is often understood as a right to expression—frequently loud and insulting—without any obligation of argumentation. Opinion becomes a substitute for judgment, and pluralism a screen behind which criteria disappear. In only apparently simple terms, pluralism is not in itself a sufficient sign of mature freedom as long as it is not accompanied by discernment and dialogue; otherwise, it degenerates—much to the detriment of the legitimate ideal—into democratic noise. It is therefore unsurprising that even today, more than three and a half decades later, one still hears claims that freedom has ruined us, that democracy is the cause of personal failure. Unable to bear the full consequences of democratic freedom, overtaken, so to speak, by the historical moment, those who invert the semantic balance so radically are in fact expressing frustration turned into revindication.

Here the central paradox of post-totalitarian freedom emerges: the less legally constrained the individual is, the more tempted they are to seek symbolic protection. This may take the form of a leader, a simplifying ideology, or an identitarian narrative—all sharing the tacit promise that judgment can be externalized at no cost. In reality, as we know, the cost is enormous—indeed, dangerous, like that of a reckless smoker in a petrol station. To put it differently: delegating discernment does not annul responsibility; it returns in the form of frustration, resentment, and ultimately the desire to punish, to avenge poorly entrusted hopes. In short, freedom not lived as a cognitive exercise rapidly becomes reivindicative freedom, oriented not toward truth, but toward symbolic satisfaction—itself a perennial source of populism that presents itself as reparative, recuperative, and healing.

To close the circle: the text of 1 Samuel 8 is not an archaic episode about monarchy, but a work of political anthropology. It describes a recurrent structure: when people grow tired of judging, they ask to be judged—that is, to be tutored—while no longer consciously participating in the mechanism of leader and led. By demanding a leader, regardless of who or how, they lose not only political freedom, but also the capacity to recognize truth as such, to distinguish between genuine and false actors of personal and social interest. This loss is not immediately visible; it manifests gradually through lowered standards, tolerance of incoherence, and acceptance of increasingly simple—if not

simplistic—explanations for realities that are, in fact, ever more complex. At this point, the ground is already prepared for the next step: the emergence of charisma as a substitute for truth, messianism as a surrogate for a national project, the savior pure and simple. A new form of dependence—not through coercion, but through affective recognition—will once again set its historical march in motion (Weber, 1922; Berdyaev, 1937; Arendt, 1951; Voegelin, 1952; Mosse, 1975; Gentile, 1993).

Charisma, deception, and false recognition: Why “feeling” is not a criterion of truth

There is a fundamental error, widely disseminated in contemporary public discourse, that makes the rapid degradation of political deliberation possible: the confusion between recognition and knowledge. The seemingly innocent formula—“I recognize him”—suspends judgment without explicitly denying it. It demands no argument, tolerates no objection, and admits no delay. Precisely for this reason, it is so effective. Where affective recognition takes the place of discernment, truth as proof becomes optional. Scripture, however, never treats recognition as a criterion of truth. On the contrary, it subjects every claimed authority to a process of verification: “Test the spirits / δοκιμάζετε τὰ πνεύματα to see whether they are from God” (1 John 4:1). The verb is decisive: to test presupposes distance, time, and criteria. Feeling is immediate; discernment is slow. For this very reason, in a culture of rapid reaction—of adhesion or rejection based on stimuli rather than ideas—feeling becomes dominant and determinant. This is hardly new to marketing as a science of capturing “spirits,” of producing states of well-being—from commerce to politics, and from culture to sport.

More than a simple exhortation to prudence, Christ situates the matter prophetically and explicitly warns about the effectiveness of deception: “False christs and false prophets will arise and will show great signs and wonders, so as to deceive, if possible, even the elect” (Matthew 24:24). The text does not speak merely of crude, obvious falsehood, but of the deceiver’s own conviction, which renders him all the more credible in the eyes of the deceived. Deception, in other words, does not operate through brutality, but through plausibility. If truth were automatically recognized through the intensity of experience alone, exclusively through the frequency of the heart, the evangelical warning would be superfluous. Worse still, it would appear as a rationalist invitation to doubt—although doubt, as an instrument of knowledge, is by no means rendered useless. In any case, if there is a constant—alongside asceticism irreducible to dietary practices—as a prerequisite for the acquisition and consolidation of virtue in the spirituality of the Eastern Church, it is the practice of enlightened judgment, of that much-invoked yet still insufficiently understood discernment (διάκρισις). Contrary to a simplifactory perception, discernment is not merely a logical exercise, a function of the mind alone, but a total engagement, involving both body and soul (Fitzmyer, 2008; Fee, 1994; Louth, 1981; Bunge, 1989, Špidlík, 1986; Marrou, 1948; Ware, 2000; Vergote, 1978; Rizzuto, 1979; Larchet, 1997; Cucci, 2010).

At this point enters the decisive contribution of a remarkable author, one of the “founders” of psychology in the strong sense of the term, and arguably the most subtle patristic analyst of the inner mechanisms of deception: Evagrius Ponticus. For Evagrius, the problem is not the content of belief, but the state of the mind that receives it. “When the mind has not attained dispassion, it cannot know the truth, for it is blinded by the passions” (Praktikos 64). The statement is strikingly radical, because for Evagrius the incapacity to know the truth is not primarily moral, but cognitive. A mind affected by passions does not discern; it merely reacts, like a system of sensors operating purely on instinct. Consequently, Evagrius explicitly warns against confusing inner movement with revelation: “Not every illumination of the mind comes from God, for even demons can bring a certain brightness in order to deceive”, Praktikos 65 (Guillaumont, 1971; 1989).

Rapid brilliance, instant certainty, the feeling of total clarity are, paradoxically, signs of epistemic danger. Authentic revelation does not excite the mind; it stabilizes it, pacifies it, and—yes—heals it when it is burdened, confused, or wounded. This observation has direct consequences for the analysis of political charisma, both past and present. Charisma, in itself, is not a pathology; it becomes dangerous when accepted without criteria. Repeatedly and demonstrably, in a context of cognitive fatigue, the charismatic leader no longer needs to demonstrate anything; it suffices that he appear “authentic.” Authenticity, however, is defined exclusively in affective, not rational, terms—hence the disregard for logical ruptures, for blatant absurdities, and for all mechanisms of verification of discourse. On the contrary, when charisma is confronted through analysis, competence, fluency, and plausibility become suspect all at once. *Sancta simplicitas!*

Evagrius goes further and identifies one of the sure signs of deception: self-assurance. “Where there is disturbance, there is no knowledge; and where there is much self-confidence, there is deception” (*Praktikos* 71). This assertion directly contradicts the contemporary culture of displayed certainty, actively promoted as such. Truth does not produce collective hysteria or affective unanimity, but clarity—that is, the capacity to endure questioning, to be tested through dialogue and controversy. In fact, the core of theological gnoseology in the Fathers—and beyond—lies in the systematic, unapologetic placing of faith in dialogue with its challengers. Christianized Greek *paideia* was nothing other than a testing of the supernatural through natural arguments, a supernatural that does not contradict human nature, but invites it to sublimation and transfiguration.

This explains why dogmatic and spiritual authority in the Church, broadly speaking, does not suffocate dilemma, eliminate doubt, or inhibit indecision, but resolves them, harmonizing them with external evidence, inner work, and the journey itself—both metaphor and reality—of faith. At the opposite pole, from an anthropological perspective, non-religious charisma exploits a regression: the return to an infantile mode of relating to authority. I know it is true because I feel good becomes the implicit criterion. In the past—and especially in the present technological age—the problem has not been the lack of information, but the refusal to undertake the effort of judgment. At this point, charisma, properly understood, is no longer an accident, but the cynical exploitation of the symptoms of an unexercised mind, of credulity—the true antonym of faith.

To draw a provisional conclusion here as well: Evagrius does not describe deception as a rare exception or an accident, but as a frequent, reproducible state of the untested mind. In other words, a mind that has not undergone the discipline of discernment will inevitably confuse movement with truth. Charisma does not, in fact, create deception; it finds it already prepared, consolidated, ready to be instrumentalized. The great problem of deception is that one cannot live indefinitely in the tension of continuously confirming a reality that is entirely different from one’s own “understanding” without becoming increasingly alienated—until, eventually, the deceiver himself loses his ground.

“They have eyes and do not see”: Senses, technology, and the exhaustion of knowledge

If the delegation of judgment and the confusion—analyzed in depth by Evagrius—between feeling and truth describe an anthropological availability for deception, what remains to be explained is the mechanism that generalizes and socially stabilizes this availability. This mechanism is not only ideological, but increasingly technological. Not because technology would possess manipulative intentions as such—though such functions can indeed be programmed—but because it shapes attention, and attention is the condition of all knowledge. Scripture formulates this diagnosis in a manner that far exceeds its historical context: “They have eyes and do not see; they have ears and do not hear” (Ps. 113:13). The text does not describe a sensory deficiency, but a rupture between the

senses and the mind. The senses function, yet they are no longer integrated into a process of understanding. Precisely this rupture is normalized today by the technological environment.

This exhaustion of discernment is not foreign to the Christian tradition and is not an invention of late modernity. It is exemplarily thematized in the episode improperly labeled the “doubt” or “unbelief” of Thomas (John 20:24–29). At a superficial reading, Thomas appears as the figure of the skeptic who refuses evidence. In reality, he refuses belief by delegation. He does not deny the possibility of the Resurrection; he refuses to substitute the experience of truth with its social recognition. “We have seen the Lord” is not, for him, a sufficient criterion. Thomas demands contact with reality, not consensus; criterion, not enthusiasm; truth, not affective confirmation—not the distribution of a post, not a viral reaction. For this reason, Christ’s response does not consist in condemning the request for verification, but in a pedagogical assumption of it: “Put your finger here [...] and do not be unbelieving, but believing.” Discernment is not suspended; it is carried through to its end. The final formula—“Blessed are those who have not seen and yet have believed”—does not proclaim the happiness of credulity, but points to the overcoming of the constraint of sensory evidence once truth has been known. In this sense, Thomas is not the figure of unbelief, but of resistance to second-hand truth. Nor is he an apostle of the rationalization of faith in scientific or experimental terms; rather, through his example, he emerges as an antidote to credulity. Precisely this demand for criteria—present at the very core of the Christian tradition, at the margin of the Resurrection itself, the foundational event—is absent from discourses that sacralize politics and demand adhesion without judgment, recognition without verification, faith without truth simply because “this is what is said,” just as Thomas’s companions once told him that the Teacher had risen from the dead.

Turning decisively to the present, it has already become commonplace to observe that informational overexposure does not produce additional knowledge, but rather the atrophy of judgment. The mind is constantly stimulated, yet increasingly rarely required to discern. The continuous flow of images, messages, and reactions transforms attention into a fragmented resource, into a mental “diaspora”—that is, dissipation. The mind works intensely and is difficult to bring into a state of repose, yet this effort yields no notable result. Nor is there, concretely and physically, time for stopping; and without stopping, without respite, there can be no discernment.

In this context, truth is not rejected so much as it is bypassed. Recent developments show that digital technology operates through confirmation rather than verification: algorithms evaluate content not according to truth or quality, but according to reaction and quantity. Consequently, what provokes affective resonance is amplified, while what demands cognitive effort is, symmetrically, marginalized and pushed out of the field of vision. From the perspective of cognitive-behavioral psychology, the criterion of truth is thus replaced by the criterion of emotional compatibility. More current than some might be willing to accept, Scripture nevertheless warns against this inversion: “Woe to those who call evil good and good evil” (Isaiah 5:20). Here again, the text is epistemological rather than moral: it describes a world in which criteria are overturned through habituation. At this point, the critique of modernity emerges from within modernity itself. Spitzer, for example, shows—on the basis of neurocognitive research—that intensive use of digital media leads to a decline in higher cognitive capacities: sustained attention, working memory, critical thinking, comparison as method, logical retroversion, and so forth. In short, the massive externalization of memory and cognitive processes does not liberate the mind, but weakens it. What is not exercised is lost, like an unused biological function or an unspoken foreign language. This is what Spitzer describes through his diagnostic formula: *digital dementia* (Spitzer, 2012; Hüther, 2011; Han, 2013; Postman, 1985; Rosa, 2016; Moltmann, 2010; Metz, 1977; Yannaras, 1984; Rose, 1994; Hart, 2013; Schmemmann, 1973).

As is well known, Neil Postman anticipated this mutation long before the advent of digital social communication networks, showing that a culture dominated by entertainment becomes incapable of distinguishing between what is serious and what is trivial—just as children fail to distinguish between the airborne movement of beloved characters and the real danger of stepping out of a window. Truth, both physical and ideational, is not prohibited, but drowned in noise, in a confusion that renders it irrelevant, that is, deprived of minimal normative force—the child leaping, in play, into full tragedy. The same holds for “grown-ups,” for whom politics becomes spectacle and choice an emotional reaction.

Byung-Chul Han goes further, describing the cumulative effect of this dynamic: an exhausted, confirmatory society, incapable of negativity or refusal—that is, of critical distance—replaces contemplation, while total transparency eliminates the inner space of judgment. In such a context, freedom is no longer constrained from without; it dissolves itself through overstimulation.

Even if it may seem redundant, it is essential to emphasize that technology does not itself create this state of cognitive blindness. It merely renders it comfortable and generalized. “I have seen” becomes equivalent to “I know.” The Gospel, however, directly contests this equivalence: “Blessed are those who have not seen and yet have believed” (John 20:29). The text does not praise ignorance, but rejects the absolutization of the senses. Truth is not guaranteed by immediate evidence, but by discernment that surpasses appearance—hence Christ’s warning not to fall into the trap of false prophets and charlatans, not to confuse the shell with the kernel.

In this context, the non-religious charisma analyzed earlier finds the perfect environment for expansion and consolidation. As we have seen in the elections initially annulled in Romania—and as we will increasingly see elsewhere—constant, visual, repetitive presence produces familiarity, and familiarity is confused with truth. At the risk of repeating what has already been stated, under such cognitive-emotional conditions the charismatic leader no longer needs to persuade; insistent, rolling visibility suffices. Even against its own intentions, when used in this manner, technology becomes the symbolic infrastructure of false recognition.

Here one of the gravest mutations of late modernity occurs: the passage from the rational—long and rightly regarded as an indispensable criterion—to the post-rational. We are not witnessing an explicit denial of reason, nor its frontal combat—how could we?—but rather its *découpage*, its “mythologization.” Argument is not rejected, but comes to be considered useless, outdated, just as truth is not combated, but—as noted from the outset—perceived as boring. At this point, we must repeat: freedom survives only as procedure, not as an exercise of the mind.

This situation raises a decisive question: might modernity, in its current form, be overextending itself into emptiness, as philosophers such as Habermas have warned? Yes, systems of choice, representation, and legitimation continue to function, but the subject capable of sustaining them cognitively is weakened to the point where we have institutions without criteria, options that are still formally real, but no longer judgment, no longer discernment (Habermas, 1985). This is not a technological crisis in the strict sense, but an anthropological one. Technology merely brings it to the surface and accelerates it. At this point, the temptation emerges to resort to another form of guaranteeing truth: the sacralization of politics. Truth, exhausted and contested, will be summoned to return in a more dangerous form.

“What is truth?”: Religion, politics, and the sacred lie

There is a foundational scene for the modern relationship between truth and power, and it does not take place in the agora, but in a closed, administrative space, devoid of solemnity. Pilate asks the

accused Christ: “What is truth?” (John 18:38). The question is famous not for its profundity, but because it does not await an answer. Pilate asks and leaves; truth is not denied, but suspended. As a result—as we know from the way Christ’s trial unfolds—truth no longer constitutes a criterion for political decision, nor for religious judgment. Christ is condemned and ultimately crucified because no one, or very few, remain capable of facing truth—truth in general—directly, eye to eye.

This scene condenses a decisive mutation: truth is acknowledged as a philosophical or religious problem, yet declared politically, that is publicly, irrelevant. This is not an absolute novelty, insofar as power, in its various definitions, does not rest on truth and must in fact avoid association with any of its versions, grounding itself instead in the management of order, as neutral as possible. In this sense, Pilate is not a historical accident, but a prototype. He is not cynical in a vulgar sense, but lucid in an administrative one—especially given his interest in preserving his position as governor. Juridically educated, he knows that truth cannot be established through procedure, and for precisely this reason procedure must function without truth, or even against it.

This very ontological hiatus is reformulated and “repaired,” invested with an entirely different meaning, by another formula equally famous: “Render to Caesar the things that are Caesar’s, and to God the things that are God’s” (Matthew 22:21). In Pilate’s “tradition,” this text is often read as legitimating the autonomy of politics from truth. In reality, it draws an ontological limit, not a functional division. The coin bears the image of Caesar just as the human being bears the image of God. Politics may administer the coin, but it cannot claim the truth about the human person without becoming idolatrous—and, as history has shown, criminal.

As Casanova and others have already observed, the problem of late modernity is not that religion returns to politics, but the manner in which it returns: as a (false) enemy or as a (false) ally. In the first instance, religion remains the absolute antithesis of political rationalism, as manifested exemplarily in the French and Bolshevik revolutions. Reason judges, condemns, and executes God through those who believe in Him. In the second instance—non-criminal, but no less problematic—religion is not assumed as a critical instance capable of limiting power, but is instrumentalized as a seal of legitimacy. God is invoked not to judge political decisions, but to render them indisputable. At this point emerges what may, without exaggeration, be called the sacred lie (Arendt, 1961; Berdyaev, 1937; Ratzinger, 2005; Brague, 2005).

The sacred lie does not consist in the mere use of religious language in the public sphere, but in the blockage of deliberation through a hypocritical appeal to transcendence. Discourse no longer says, “this is my option,” but “this is the will of God.” Any objection thus becomes not only political, but sacrilegious. Truth is confiscated not in order to be known, but in order to be sealed off. Consequently, at the level of campaign discourse, it suffices to replace God with “the people” or “the nation,” “tradition” or “genius,” for the struggle waged in their name to acquire crusading overtones and for politics to paint itself with a halo.

Augustine formulates one of the most lucid limits of political power in its recurrent attempt at self-deification. In *The City of God*, he states unequivocally that a state lacking justice—that is, lacking rational virtue—is nothing other than a latrocinium, a band of robbers. This observation is often read moralistically, which is not entirely incorrect, but its deeper stake is epistemological: justice is not possible without truth, and truth cannot be produced by power without being corrupted and falsified—hence the perversion of justice itself. In continuity with Christian realism, already evident in the earliest generations during the time of persecutions, despite eschatological excesses, Augustine by no means demonizes the state, as an expression of human autonomy, but he refuses its claim to ultimate authority in order to avoid having to accept its tyranny (Markus, 1970; Elshtain, 1995).

At this point, a bridge becomes necessary to one of the most serious modern attempts to preserve political rationality without reducing it to technique: the deliberative ethics formulated by the frequently invoked Habermas. His intention is clear: practical truth cannot be imposed, but neither can it be dissolved into subjective preferences. It must result from a process of free and symmetrical argumentation, constrained only by the force of the better argument. The problem arises when the anthropological conditions of deliberation are presupposed but no longer real. Deliberative ethics functions only where the subject is capable of distance from the self, of self-correction, and of accepting symbolic loss in favor of a higher rationality, the common good.

Yet precisely these capacities are eroded in the previously described context: cognitive fatigue, algorithmic confirmation, and charismatic sacralization empty deliberation of its subject. The risk is not that deliberation is too demanding, too insistent, too “intimate,” but that it becomes purely procedural, formal, external to the subject. Dialogue turns into a juxtaposition of unresolved opinions, and consensus into a negotiation of affects unilluminated by reason. Paradoxical but explicable, what in Habermas is conceived as a transcendence of subjectivism risks becoming its legitimation if there are no longer minds capable of directly sustaining the normative force of the argument and the negotiated common alterity, so to speak.

At this point, truth is trapped between two forms of negation: Pilate’s cynicism (“truth does not matter”) and the sacred lie (“truth is already decided”). In both cases, freedom is fundamentally affected. Once again, truth ceases to be something to be known, something worthy even of curiosity, becoming either useless or downright dangerous—and therefore undesirable (Habermas, 1983; 1996; 1999; 2008). A return to the fundamental evangelical affirmation thus becomes, inevitably, necessary: “You will know the truth, and the truth will make you free” (John 8:32). Once again: truth is not the product of freedom, but its condition. When truth is suspended by cynicism or confiscated through sacralization—through sacrilegious appropriation—freedom survives only as form, not as lived reality. This double diversion prepares the ground for the final diagnosis: it is not institutions that fail first, but the mind. And it is here that the ultimate stake of post-totalitarian modernity is decided.

The post-totalitarian mind: Epistemic shame and the condition of freedom

There is a point beyond which political, sociological, or theological analysis becomes insufficient. That point is the mind itself. Not as psychological abstraction and not as mere “public opinion,” but as the organ of knowledge, the place where truth is either recognized or lost. Everything is decided here. Not in institutions, not in procedures, not in elections, but in the capacity to know that one does not know. This is the final and most uncomfortable theme of our study: *epistemic shame*. Not moral shame, nor social shame, but that inner hesitation without which knowledge does not begin, or is postponed, frozen “in project,” to borrow Liiceanu’s formulation. The human being who no longer possesses this shame is not free, but merely self-assured—and self-assurance, in the absence of truth, is the mature, “consolidated” form of deception, the basis of verbal violence and, very soon, of physical violence.

It is therefore likely insufficient simply to remind ourselves that the post-totalitarian mind is marked by a double and contradictory inheritance. On the one hand, it was formed under a regime of imposed truth, usually through physical violence and, until the regime’s collapse, through psychological terror; autonomous thinking was not only forbidden, but dangerous. The so-called communist “new man” was required to feel remorse for the “heresies” he might have thought, for sinful ideas—much like the ascetic’s self-critical conscience struggling with thoughts, with immaterial fabrications which, once admitted into the heart, become deeds. In other words, a spiritual ascent like that of the *Philokalia*, but entirely and perversely inverted.

Indeed, if we examine the intellectual history of communism—especially Soviet communism—we encounter sadomasochistic figures, tragic caricatures of Job who accept their cruel fate as the well-deserved payment for an unforgivable infidelity to the ideal. This mental structure explains why, in the Moscow Trials, for example, the accused not only submit to the verdict, but internalize it, transforming torture into a necessary form of ideological tribunal. Guilt, where it truly exists, is no longer linked to deeds, but to insufficient devotion, while death becomes, within the system’s logic, an act of moral hygiene. Within the same horizon falls the fate of Mandelstam, to offer one biographical example, whose biological annihilation in the camp is not merely political repression, but punishment inflicted upon the body for refusing to dissolve completely into historical mythology.

Even ambiguous cases, such as that of Benjamin, reveal the exhaustion of a conscience that can no longer find an exit between fidelity to a compromised ideal and the moral impossibility of continuing to support it. By contrast, in Steinhardt, Ioanid, or Solzhenitsyn, carceral suffering is not internalized as guilt, but becomes, behind bars, liberation from all fear. Suffering thus does not legitimate the system; it exposes it, remaining the place of refusal to consent to falsehood and of preserving the freedom of conscience (Miłosz, 1953; Koestler, 1940; Grossman, 1959; Todorov, 1991; Steinhardt, 20204; Leford, 1981).

On the other hand, the same mind—regardless of age, up to a chronological threshold not yet reached—today lives under a regime of unlimited opinions, where autonomous thinking appears superfluous. As repeatedly argued above, between constraint and dilution, between the physical and the psychological, the mind has learned a reflex: the avoidance of judgment, the refusal to test the spirits, the suspension of discernment. This evasion is not passive, but active, expressed through the substitution of knowledge with feeling, discernment with affective recognition, truth with confirmation. “I feel” becomes the formula that shortens every path toward truth. “I feel” demands no proof, tolerates no contradiction, and admits no time. From this point on, the mind exits the regime of knowledge and enters that of reaction.

Evagrius once again describes this mechanism with remarkable precision and modernity. For him, discernment begins not with enthusiasm, but with stopping—with an ascetic inhibition. A mind that moves too quickly, restlessly, cannot see the truth, being in danger of instantly confusing movement with illumination. Hence Evagrius insists that the first condition of knowledge is the calming of the mind, its non-discursive—and therefore non-reactive—ordering and discipline. As noted above, this intuition is devastating for the contemporary culture of continuous reaction. Translated for the contemporary subject, the Evagrian lesson would read as follows: without pause there is no discernment, just as without discernment truth remains inaccessible even when it is present.

Maximus the Confessor refines this insight through the characteristic patristic method of drilling both downward and upward, showing that the problem becomes critical when the will detaches itself from reason. The will desires the good, but no longer knows how to recognize it. It chooses, but without criterion. This is the exact description of the contemporary political subject: active, mobilized, participatory, yet cognitively weak. As we observe in all civic and political movements, without exception, energy is not lacking—indeed, it overflows, even into physical and verbal violence—but orientation toward truth is missing. The goal is not understood as a mere promise, but—using a biblical term adopted from the ancients—as *τέλος*, a horizon fulfilled in the very process of becoming, which invests the time leading toward it with meaning.

Another major reference in Eastern patristics, Isaac the Syrian, introduces a decisive correction: knowledge does not begin with the accumulation of information, but with the humility of the mind. Humility, contrary to common usage, is neither self-abasement nor suspicion toward reason, but the

recognition of one's own limits. We encounter the same schema once again: the person who knows that he does not know remains open to truth, whereas the person who is certain that he knows is already closed—not *into*, as Noica would put it. This observation stands in direct conflict with the contemporary culture of displayed opinions, where certainty is rewarded and doubt penalized.

If epistemic shame appears as a lost virtue, saying “I do not know” becomes a sign of weakness—when, in reality, it is the beginning of freedom. Without this shame, the human being can no longer learn, can no longer correct, and can no longer discern. He is no longer persuaded, but merely confirmed—and, as is well known (*sic!*), confirmation does not liberate; it encloses one within the carnivorous cup of populism, political messianism, and, more generally, patterns that are as paradoxical as they are noisy. This is the condition the present study has sought to describe from various angles: a society in which systems of choice function, but the subject of choice is weakened; in which procedure remains, but truth disappears; in which the religious is summoned to legitimate, not to judge.

The crisis is therefore not primarily political or institutional, but anthropological. It would, however, be a grave mistake to read this diagnosis in a fatalistic key, if only because biblical and patristic tradition never legitimates resignation. The Cross is not the symbol of defeat, but of deferred victory. In other words, just as in the communion of faith, so too in the broader community, the Pauline call to “the renewal of the mind” (τῆ ἀνακαινώσει τοῦ νοός, Romans 12:2) is more relevant than ever. It is not a pious metaphor, but a demanding, continuous labor, as important as a national or societal project. It presupposes relearning the critical pause—education being its privileged mechanism—the acceptance of fertile doubt through a culture of dialogue, and the refusal of prepackaged certainties through loyal competition of ideas (Williams, 2002; Fricker, 2007; Florovsky, 1979; Karakolis, 2013; Zizioulas, 1985).

A return to the fundamental evangelical affirmation closes the circle: “You will know the truth, and the truth will make you free” (John 8:32). Since truth, as argued throughout, is not the product of freedom but its condition, wherever truth is replaced by feeling, charisma, technology, or political sacralization, freedom withers—even if its external forms, procedures, institutions, or special pensions survive. The present study, explicitly social-theological in character, does not propose political solutions or institutional recipes. It proposes something more difficult: the rehabilitation of the mind. Without it, neither democracy, nor faith, nor freedom can be saved. With it, all remain *salvable*.

An open conclusion: Truth, discernment and the fragility of freedom

At the risk of repetition—but in order to fix as clearly and firmly as possible the theses of Orthodox social theology and its method of reading—these pages have not sought to explain a specific electoral episode, nor to formulate an alternative theory of democracy. Their stake has been more delicate and, for that very reason, more uncomfortable: the identification of the anthropological conditions of freedom in a post-totalitarian context marked by the fatigue of judgment, the unchecked expansion of charisma, and the degradation of deliberation.

The analysis has shown that freedom is rarely lost through spectacular acts of coercion. It is more often eroded through the gradual delegation of discernment—step by step, as a contemporary expression would put it. When judgment is abandoned—out of fear, convenience, or cognitive saturation—freedom survives only formally. Elections remain, procedures continue to function, but truth ceases to serve as a criterion. In this void, affective recognition replaces knowledge, and charisma substitutes for argument.

As has, we trust, become clear, the role of technology is not genuinely to create this condition, but to normalize and accelerate it. Continuous confirmation, the fragmentation of attention, and cognitive fatigue empty the deliberative space of the subject capable of sustaining it. Under such circumstances, deliberative ethics risks transforming itself from a normative ideal into a contentless procedure, while pluralism degenerates into a mere juxtaposition of irreconcilable opinions.

Against this background, the return of religion to the public sphere does not automatically correct the deficit. On the contrary. When transcendence is instrumentalized in order to block deliberation, what emerges is what we have called the *sacred lie*: the confiscation of truth not in order to be known, but in order to be sealed off. Truth thus becomes trapped between two convergent forms of negation: the cynicism that declares it useless and the pseudo-sacralization that renders it indisputable.

At this point, the diagnosis becomes inevitable and, at the limit, painful: the crisis of freedom is, ultimately, a crisis of the mind. Institutions are not the first to fail; the capacity to discern is. For this reason, purely political or technical solutions remain insufficient. They may repair procedures, but they cannot rehabilitate criteria.

Biblical and patristic tradition, however, indicate an exit that is neither utopian nor fatalistic, nor even exclusively theological: the renewal of the mind. This entails the recovery of epistemic shame, the acceptance of one's own limits, and the refusal of facile—suspiciously facile—certainties. Without this effort, truth remains either dangerous or boring. With it, and through it, freedom—even fragile and exposed as we see it today—remains possible.

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